

The knife is then turned at an angle of forty-five degrees, and downward and outward. This, on the cadaver, has been proved to throw the posterior ethmoidal labyrinth pretty thoroughly open every time. By means of the pharyngoscope it is found that there are two very satisfactory openings into the posterior ethmoidal cell, and sometimes the sphenoidal. Sometimes it is possible to get it all out in that way. Dr. Wright has one such specimen, measuring a half inch in diameter.

DR. COAKLEY spoke of being unable to get good observation with the pharyngoscope. I always operate under cocain. I uniformly refuse to operate upon these patients except under cocain. I give them scopolamin first. The primary stroke is sufficient to produce enough shock, and at the same time to prevent the wound from bleeding. With the pharyngoscope close at hand it can be passed in. The patient may faint; let him faint. The wound for a time does not bleed.

I have some cases in which the opening stayed open for five or six years. I have never seen membranous closure, as suggested by Dr. Bryan, but I have seen bony closure, as suggested by Dr. Coakley.

DR. LOEB spoke of congestion in the sinus, which he thought more responsible than the vacuum of which I spoke. Politzerization will stop the trouble. The congestion is the result of the vacuum.

DR. LELAND has given a valuable point about the little pressure of long standing.

I have tried vaccines repeatedly, as suggested by Dr. Logan, but have not gotten the results.

DR. MAYER spoke of crises and the use of ergot. In my text I brought out, partly as a matter of speculation, that there is in some canals a considerable pad of fat; in the optic canal there is exceedingly little. If this hyperplastic process narrows the canal and this pressure is maintained for a considerable time, nature's shock absorber is used up. Sometimes a trifling indigestion will start up the trouble, just as sometimes a trifling thing will diminish the vision. If ergot is given when there is this congestion, it will contract the tissues and relieve the headache.

DR. STOUT, closing the discussion: I merely wish to say, with reference to Dr. Casselberry's remarks, that I distinctly said there was apparently no pus.

The Effects of Radioactivity Upon Nasopharyngeal Fibroma. DR. D. BRYSON DELAVAN, NEW YORK CITY.

The conditions due to the presence of this growth are usually so urgent as to demand relief.

For this three varieties of treatment have thus far been practiced:

1. Removal of the tumor after preliminary operation done for the removal of obstructing parts.
2. Removal through the natural passages by evulsion or with the cold snare.
3. The reduction of the size and the vascularity of the tumor by electrolysis or by the injection of various chemicals, followed by the removal of the remaining mass by means of the galvanocautic loop.

Of these methods the first is illogical, unsurgical, and, as experience has abundantly proved, deadly; shock from the preliminary operation

is severe, hemorrhage profuse, and if the patient survive, deformity from the preliminary operation is serious and recurrence of the growth common.

The second method is much better than the first, but may provoke serious hemorrhage and shock, and is apt to be followed by recurrence.

The third method is by far the best. Although tedious and sometimes painful and requiring considerable skill, statistical comparison shows that of twenty-seven cases removed after severe preliminary operation in which end results were given, fifty-nine per cent were reported "cured" and twenty-six per cent died. Of forty-one cases removed through the natural passages by evulsion or the cold snare, five per cent died; and of sixty-six cases by electrical methods, one hundred per cent were cured.

Much attention has of late been given to the treatment of uterine and other fibromata by means of the X-ray and of radium, and both in the United States and in Europe the apparent success attained renders the method worthy of consideration. The similarity of type between the uterine and pharyngeal growths at once attracts the attention of the laryngologist to the new treatment.

Fibromata of the nasopharynx are relatively much smaller and more directly accessible.

The complete reduction of the nasopharyngeal growth might not be essential, since it tends to diminish spontaneously after adolescence and finally disappears. If its growth could be controlled during the earlier years and until after the period of its activity, nature would in some cases at least intervene to effect a cure. Cases of slow development occurring in older rather than younger patients would offer the best prognosis. Judging from the effects of radium in other cases, its action would be active and profound: more may reasonably be expected from it than a moderate reduction in size.

Dr. Robert Abbe, pioneer in the use of radium in the United States, has originated many ingenious devices for its application to various organs of the body, and especially for its use in the nasal and nasopharyngeal region.

In the application of the radium, the parts to be treated must be exposed to the rays, and the healthy surrounding parts must be protected from them. It is not necessary that the radium should be introduced bodily into the substance of the growth, as the blood vessels of the growth are more abundant near its surface, and as the rays penetrate at least a quarter of an inch, the treatment is entirely effective in profoundly influencing the circulation, and thus, as well as by its effect upon the connective tissue of the organ, causing a reduction of its size. Proper regulation of the strength of the radium and the duration of the exposure will prevent injury to the surrounding healthy parts. Should the radium treatment prove as valuable as it promises, the world may be congratulated that the unhappy record of past surgical failure will have been closed.

DISCUSSION.

DR. CORNELIUS G. COAKLEY, New York City: Dr. Francis Carter Wood has been experimenting, as all know, on various animal colonies with radium: he has also done some clinical work with this agent. He has

been kind enough to use it in several cases which I have sent him during the past year and a half. In a case of epithelioma of the nose, radium had a very favorable effect. The patient had a bad case of arteriosclerosis and died from cardiac trouble. All trace of the epithelioma had disappeared. Several cases of papilloma of the larynx were cured by radium. In one case the papilloma had existed from early childhood to the age of forty or more. In another case treated by him there was an angiofibroma which completely filled the nasal cavity, the mass being visible without a nasal speculum. He used eighteen milligrams in a very small glass tube wrapped in ordinary adhesive tape. This was thrust into the nose, and was followed by profuse bleeding. At the end of two weeks no change in the mass could be noted. For some reason the boy did not return to the clinic for eight or ten days, and when he returned it was found that the mass had decreased in size. A brass capsule containing eighty-three milligrams of radium was then inserted, the posterior end of this tube extending into the posterior nasopharynx. This was left in for twenty-four hours. The excoriation all around the face was simply remarkable. No X-ray burn ever compared with this burn. Dr. Wood told me I need not worry about it, as it would disappear, which it did. The radium was applied in February, and the inside has not completely healed. The patient can breathe through the nose, however, and it is possible to look right through into the nasopharynx. The mass is attached to the posterior wall of the nares and apparently somewhere in the posterior ethmoidal region on the left side. Since the radium has been used the hemorrhages which the patient had at irregular intervals have almost entirely ceased. The radium is pretty apt to cure this fibroma. A smaller dose in this case would probably have been better.

DR. OTTO T. FREER, Chicago: I have used radium, but not in the treatment of fibroma. We have at our command a means which we did not have a few years ago. I have removed a very large fibromata, with a keen knife, from behind, after having injected directly into the growth a double dose of pituitary extract, two ampullae, followed by adrenalin. The hemorrhage did not exsanguinate the patient. There has been one recurrence since.

Would not the combination of surgery with radium be less tedious and more satisfactory than radium alone in the removal of fibroma that enters all the cavities?

I was interested in the recovery which Dr. Coakley reported. Dr. Frank Dudley Simpson, of Chicago, who has employed it so extensively, says he has never had a recovery. I would like to ask Dr. Coakley how long after the use of the radium the burn appeared, and how long the radium was used.

DR. COAKLEY, continuing the discussion: This is not the only burn which has come under my observation. I recall a case treated by Kelly, in which there was a most terrific burn, resulting in extensive infiltration and suppuration. That was a year ago last December. There was a recurrence of the epithelioma of the larynx, and the patient went down some time in March for further treatment. The radium was used without

external reaction, but with such extensive internal reaction, with swelling of the arytenoid folds and aryepiglottic tissues, that it was almost necessary to do a tracheotomy.

In the case I cited, the boy had had no treatment for a week, when superficial ulceration appeared all over the skin of the nose and cheek. It was extraordinarily painful. The pain following the use of radium is what patients object to. There is no question of its activity.

DR. DELAVAN, closing the discussion: I cannot conceal my great satisfaction with regard to the cases which Dr. Coakley has presented. I have been studying this matter of nasopharyngeal fibroma ever since I was an undergraduate student. I have seen the best surgeons take these cases and end with very unsatisfactory results. Statistics show that surgical procedures of any kind are dangerous. Evulsion, removal with a snare, and other methods, may be followed by hemorrhage. As far as I can compile statistics on the subject, there are five deaths in a hundred, as the result of shock or hemorrhage. There is always the danger of recurrence. The application of radium requires a certain amount of skill, but no surgical skill.

Sodium Bicarbonate in Hay-fever. K. E. KELLOGG, *N. Y. Med. Jour.*, Aug. 21, 1915.

Kellogg is of the opinion that hay-fever is essentially an acidosis and by reason of certain irritating qualities of the blood the mucous membranes become hypersensitive. His experience covers fifty cases and in ninety per cent. of them sodium bicarbonate given in dram doses three times a day produced a marked amelioration of symptoms, of which seventy per cent. were completely relieved after a few days' treatment. The remaining ten per cent. were also benefitted, although not so markedly as the others.

The improvement of the local symptoms seemed to be independent of the exciting cause (cotton weed, rag weed, wild rose, golden rod). In three cases the internal administration of the sodium bicarbonate was supplemented by a nasal spray with a solution of the same alkali.

Kellogg suggests that the sodium bicarbonate acts by preventing the pollen toxins from going into solution.

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